

MEANING TREASURE FOR TOBACCO FARMERS IN TEMANGGUNG, CENTRAL JAVA, INDONESIA

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Abstract- condition farmer tobacco in a manner economy seen more prosperous. But style life they extravagant make economy they in a manner material no lots develop on sector productive. This study aim want to see how meaning treasure for farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk, Temanggung. Method which used is with use approach qualitative, phenomenology. Research results show that farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk, interpret treasure at the time harvest is matter prestige, so in a manner economical they more choose for use treasure them in the sector consumptive than productive.

Keywords: tobacco farmer , meaning , treasure , phenomenology

INTRODUCTION

Development in various sector need synergy between stakeholders from a number of field which involve all aspect. Wrong one field which must noticed is field agriculture. Indonesia as country agrarian have priority which more in agriculture. Wrong one sector agriculture which give donation the size of the state budget is commodity tobacco . Every Indonesia produces annually tobacco on average as much as 180 thousand tons. There are a total of 5.9 million power work capable absorbed from sector manufacturing and distribution as much 4,2 million, for the rest work in sector plantation as much 1,7 million (Hidayat, Mardialina, and Savitri, 2021).

On basically role sector agriculture development Indonesia directed for increase production agriculture so that can fulfilled need food, increase export and push even distribution chance in trying. For example in field business sector agriculture which enough role in Indonesia that is about agriculture tobacco which there is in Regency Temanggung (Masruroh, 2015).

Wrong one ability sector his farm that can give contribution in a manner direct to growth economy and welfare house ladder farmer. This matter because exists increase on level income and surplus which generated from the sector. So , increase level income become determinant main well-being house ladder farmer and 2 one factor important for conditioning growth economy (Prasetio, 2018). Based on Constitution Republic of Indonesia Number 11 Year 2009 about well-being social explain that condition the already fulfilled with various need such as material, spiritual, and social so that public the own life which worthy as well as capable for develop self with method carry out function social in Indonesia.

Lots of commodities cultivated in Indonesia one of them that is plant tobacco. Plant tobacco is plant which own uniqueness, so that in every area have characteristic typical each and quality produced by plants tobacco different. Plant the own characteristic typical which in where can influenced by various aspect especially on aspect environment and the cultivation process carried out by farmers in the area.

On three year final price tobacco in Regency Temanggung experience decline. In matter this, can seen because exists difference price with resulting quality more Good from harvest before. Year 2018 prices plant tobacco reach range as big IDR 50,000.00 up to IDR 60,000.00 per kilogram. Whereas for moment this price plant tobacco reach range as big Rp 35,000.00 until Rp 45,000.00 per kilogram. With so in between both of them there is exists difference which though big, so that will impact on farmers tobacco. So, got resulted decline income received by farmers tobacco. It is too will influence well-being farmer tobacco naturally in area Regency Temanggung (BPS, 2018).

Wrong one indicator which can used for see level well-being a farmer is through his income. The more tall level well-being para farmer so will influential on income, wide land, long education, amount child, and gender. So that ell-being para farmer tobacco become more ok, so must he did with method obtain income which more big. With exists activity business para farmer tobacco this expected can increase income so that can fulfil need everyday (Soekartawi, 2000).

Same as most workers in other areas, farmers tobacco too have family must they enough needs at home. They must try maximum possible for fulfil need house ladder with results from work their farmers do. order them can sufficient his needs no a little from they do work side outside his job as farmer. Income clean farmers tobacco from do ricefield also can be measured from results work side which done by the farmers. For example just from land non fields worked by farmers like fields, gardens mix, and fields . Besides that there is farmer which get income besides from activity non agriculture, for example like open stall, become craftsman taxibike, labourer building and work side other which can determine well-being house ladder farmer such, so can analyzed through total revenue house ladder farmer for determine magnitude income somebody (Khanisa, 2013).

Well-being farmer no only be measured with material like level income.farmers tobacco this often faced on various problem which precisely rather raises loss for himself alone. The problem like pollution land And water, change climate , poisoning pesticide on moment spraying, and damage land consequence use material chemistry with high dose. Various type type impact the can resulted decline level well-being farmers and society also. Because by that pattern exploitation possible tobacco increase benefits and pressing various type impact negative need developed Again (Damhuri, 2017).

Income farmer tobacco can categorized as tall If compared to with farmer from commodity besides tobacco, even There is term Which say that tobacco is gold green. Condition this which sometimes make farmer tobacco more believe self in spend results harvest . From the results Lestari's research (2018) found that data farmer very consumptive, tend no own planning financial and only for prestige or style live. The resulting impact that is purchased items no beneficial or redundant, no investment capital tobacco in years future so that farmer must loan money to the bank because no own savings money (Lestari, 2018). This aligned with results observation village writer Hamlet Lamuk, Village Legoksari , District Tlogomulyo, Regency Temanggung. Most of farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk utilise treasure results harvest for buy goods consumptive . Phenomenon style life luxurious the farmers tobacco in the District Temanggung always happen over and over again post season harvest .

Farmer tobacco feel more own high prestige if capable buy goods luxurious after harvest. Desire farmer this sometimes no in accordance with main need them, and more brought to condition extravagant. This in accordance with narrative of one farmers in Lamuk, Blumud (61 y.o) at the time interview study preliminary on November 1st, 2022, infoman state that desire for buy goods tertiary, car for example, this is because he want to considered as successful farmer when moment harvest. Observation data prefix researchers also pointed out similar thing, that is lots vehicle new which owned a number of family farmer in Hamlet Lamuk. Condition luxury on moment harvest it turns out no aligned with style life daily farmer. On observation and interviews at the beginning with a number of farmers in Lamuk , in fact shows the data, that they only eat with utilise results cultivation plant food from their garden or ricefield. Expenditure consumptive daily farmer enough little, even they average only spend their money for buy food that they cannot production in a manner directly, like sugar, salt, tea and so on. This interesting for studied, how contrast life daily with condition their post harvest. So that, researcher want to analyze the meaning treasure actually for farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk, Village Legoksari, District Tlogomulyo, Regency Temanggung.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Study related about tobacco has lots done by researchers before a number of study the among them is theme study about commodity tobacco, theme about the resulting product that is cigarettes, drugs and others, as well related theme with farmer tobacco. In part this, researcher will write a number of study previous ones become reference so that study This no repeat study which already done by researchers before.

First , research conducted by Runtiko, Trisakti, Witjaksono (2018) in Hamlet Lamuk, Temanggung with title Exploration Wisdom Local Business farmer Tobacco Srinthil on the Slopes Mountain cleft. Research results show that wisdom local business farmer tobacco consists on three category main : rituals traditional, design home, and spirit of work. Besides as business for look for Srinthil, local wisdom business farmer tobacco also function as media transmission mark intergenerational, means prayer to God, preservation natural or environment, and maintenance cohesion social. Study Runtiko, Trisakti, Witjaksono (2018) use approach qualitative with method studies case. Equality with study moment this is on location study that is Hamlet Lamuk, and object study that is public Hamlet Lamuk, Temanggung.

Second, study Deny Setiawan year 2015 which loaded on Journal resilience National Against resilience Economy Family (Study in the Village Campur Sari, District Bulu, Regency Temanggung, Province Central Java). Results study show that behavior farmer in spend the money post harvest highway tobacco trend implications negative resilience economy family farmer. Study Setiawan (2015), use method descriptive qualitative. Equality with study this is theme study that is related with management treasure results harvest tobacco. Differences in methods and location research.

Third, research conducted by Lorensia, Pratama and Yudianto (2016) Intrepretative Phenomenological Analysis : Perception of Health Risk of Smoking and Smoking Cessation Among Pharmacy Students on year 2016. Results study the is all participant understand risk and consequence smoking , and before has try stop smoke because smoke influence life they, cause problem finance and health. Equality with study this is use studies phenomenology. Difference study on object and location research.

Fourth, Hasyim's research (2018) entitled The Determinants Of Rural Poverty (A Study of Tobacco farmers in Temanggung). Results study describe capacity, culture, empowerment government, capital social and religiosity as variable free influence attitude the community on turn influence empowerment public poor as effort countermeasures poverty. This study use approach quantitative with method SEM analysis. Equality with study this is on object study that is farmer tobacco.

Study related ins and outs about tobacco has lots done by researcher before. A number of study the among them is theme study about commodity tobacco, theme about product which generated that is cigarette, drug and etc, as well as theme which related with farmer tobacco. Study which there is tend see farmer and life farmer tobacco from corner view social or person other.

Novelty study this is see phenomenon tobacco and farmer from different sides, ie farmer tobacco from corner view self they alone about meaning something value. This study will use method of phenomenology to see how the tobacco farmer interpret treasure moment postharvest.

METHOD

This study use paradigm constructivist. This study is study qualitative with use approach phenomenology. Study phenomenology that is type study qualitative seeing and hearing more near and detailed explanation and understanding individual about his experiences. Study qualitative including in study qualitative pure because in implementation based on effort understand as well as describe characteristic features intrinsic from phenomena that occur on self alone (Eko Sugianto, 2015). Phenomenology interpreted also as view thinking that emphasizes focus experiences and story subjective people and interpretation on implementation in the world (Moleong, 2017).

Research process this will shared into the three stage that is stage orientation or description, stage reduction or focus, and stage selection. Process study qualitative can depicted as a foreigner would see show something stage art, foreigners That not yet know what, why, and how art it. So after see, observe and analyze with carefully then will know and understand (Sugiyono, 2016) Research this will done with describe results interview and observation on subject study that is farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk,

then result will reduced in accordance with research data needs and the last will selecting the part to be in analysis that is meaning treasure for farmer tobacco.

Source data this study is data primary and secondary. Data primary in this study is data which obtained direct from person first or person concerned in this study or informant, that is farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk, Village Legoksari, District Tlogomulyo, Regency Temanggung. A number of party informant farmer will chosen by purposive sampling. Type interview used is semi structured interview. Interview this later will develop on moment interview going on. Besides that, data primary also will done with observation straight to life farmer post harvest tobacco. Secondary data in research this is the data obtained from related journals and books with life farmer tobacco as well as photo and documentation preacher farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk.

Data analysis performed in this study with use method phenomenology data analysis or known with term FDA. Analysis data used for objective zoom out And limit discoveries so that become an orderly data, structured, more arranged and more own meaning. In other words, data analysis can interpreted as a process simplification of the data obtained to in more shape easy for understood and translated so that capable implemented.

On research this, the steps are taken for test data validity is with triangulation source, validity source means study use source person from various party so that can each other complete and test. Triangulation source will done with method crosscheck answer from one source information with source information which other. Answer from farmer one will cross checked with answer farmer else, answer informant will cross checked with data observation or observation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Farmer Tobacco

The term "peasant" of lots circles academic social will give various meanings and definitions. Figure farmer have Lots dimensions, so that various circles give view in accordance with which features dominant. Moore in the book social origins of Dictatorship and Democracy and Peasant in the Making of the Modern World (1966) notes three characteristics farmers, namely: legal subordination, specificity cultural, and de facto ownership of ground, kindly general understanding farmer is someone who works for fulfil need his life from activity business agriculture, good form business agriculture in the field plant food, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry, and fishery. Mosher (1987) gives limitation that farmer is working man look after plant and or animal for taken the benefits to use produce income. Limitation farmer according to Department Agriculture The Republic of Indonesia is perpetrator main agribusiness, fine agribusiness monoculture nor polyculture from commodity plant food, horticulture, animal husbandry, fishery and or commodity plantation.

Characteristic features public farmer as following: 1) units family (home stairs) farmer is unit base in public dimensional village double, 2) farmer life from farming, with process land, 3) pattern culture farmer characterized traditional and typical, and 4) farmer occupy position low in society, they is 'person small' to public in over-village (Sajogyo, 1999). As for farmer small " with characteristic features as following: 1) try farming in pressure resident local which increases, 2) has resource limited so that create level life which low, 3) depend entirely or part to subsistence production, and 4) not enough obtain service health, education, and service others. (Arie Sujito, 2013). From concepts and definitions on hence, farmer tobacco can interpreted as perpetrator main agribusiness commodity tobacco. On study This farmer tobacco restricted on farmer tobacco in Lamuk, Legoksari, Temanggung.

Treasure For Farmer

Kindly terminology, treasure is all something which pleasant man and they maintain, good in form material nor in benefits (Hasan, 2003). There is also a meaning with something that needed and obtained man good form object which looked like gold, silver, animals, plants, or not looks, ie benefit like vehicle, clothes, and place stay. Because that, something which no mastered man no can named treasure, like birds in the air, fish in ocean off, tree in forest, and goods mine which there is in earth (Syafei, 2000).

Treasure on study this is all something which obtained farmer from results harvest cultivation tobacco in form money, vehicle, land and so on. Farmer tobacco as wrong one crutch agribusiness in Indonesia, looked at as weak party because income those too small. However, share part farmer tobacco matter the no apply. Price commodity classified tobacco tall cause style life they including hedonic/extravagant. Life farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk, Regency Temanggung wrong one example which real. Lots between they which own characteristic excessive in treasure moment they harvest. Treasure for they moment harvest is a prestige and pride that showed with buy goods consumer can seen in a manner direct, like vehicle, house or jewelery. Currently treasure for fulfil need daily no matter which important. Circumstances this sometimes trick circumstances they which actually moment harvest. Part they which loss, force self for seen succeed harvest so that sometimes must buy with use money debt. Life the make farmer tobacco as perpetrator the economy looks rich, however actually condition they the same with public farmer other.

Phenomenology looked object and incident from perspective recipient (Littlejohn, 1999). Approach this is something which method assume that events and objects left what exists without exists intervention researcher. A researcher phenomenology no do hypothesis, however in a manner be careful test experience life actual for looked like what experience the happened. If researcher want to know what that "love", researcher no ask to psychologist, but researcher enter on experience personal about love.

Stanley Deetz conclude that there is three principle base phenomenology: First, knowledge about awareness. Knowledge no conclusion from experience, but got in a manner direct from experience conscious. Second, meaning "something" depends on important nope "something" that in life someone. With say other, how researcher connect object potential with meaning object the. Third, language is means understand meaning. Every individual experience life in world with language which used for define and express all something which there is in the world (Littlejohn, 1999).

Temporary phenomenology according to Edmund Husserl (Kuswarno, 2009) ie learn forms experience from corner look at that person experience it in a manner direct, as it were si researcher experience it alone. Phenomenology no just classify every action aware which done, but also includes prediction to future action come, seen from aspects which related with him. Everything that

sourced from how somebody interpret object in the experience. Because that, it's not wrong if phenomenology is also interpreted as studies about meaning, where meaning that more wide from just language which represent it (Afdjani, Soleh Soemirat, 2010). From the results Lestari's research (2018) found that data farmer very consumptive, tend no own planning financial and only for prestige or style live. The resulting impact that is purchased items no beneficial or redundant, no investment capital tobacco in years future so that farmer must borrow money to the bank because no own savings money (Lestari, 2018), this aligned with results observation village writer Hamlet Lamuk, Village Legoksari, District Tlogomulyo, Regency Temanggung. Part big farmer tobacco in Hamlet Lamuk utilise treasure results harvest for buy goods consumptive. Phenomenon style life luxurious the farmers tobacco in the Regency Temanggung always happen over and over again post season harvest.

Conclusion

Farmer tobacco as one crutch agribusiness in Indonesia, viewed as weak side because income those too small. However, for part farmer tobacco matter the no apply. Price commodity tobacco which belong tall cause style life they including hedonic/extravagant. Life farmer tobacco in Lamuk, Temanggung, one of them example which real. Lots between they which own characteristic excessive in treasure moment they harvest. Treasure for they moment harvest is a prestige, and pride that showed with buy goods the consumptive can seen in a manner direct, like vehicle, house or jewelery. Currently treasure for fulfil need daily no matter which important. Circumstances this sometimes trick circumstances they which actually moment harvest. Part they which loss, force self for seen succeed harvest so that sometimes must buy with use money debt. Life the make farmer tobacco as perpetrator the economy seen rich, however actually condition they the same with public farmer other. Because that, important for service related for give counseling related style life which more healthy and efficient so that farmer tobacco can utilise results harvest they for things productive.

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